

RemNavi Remote Job Market Methodology

Data Aggregation, Transparency Scoring, and Open-Data Standards

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Dezső Mező

DField Kft., Dunakeszi, Hungary
press@remnavi.com · <https://remnavi.com>

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Abstract

RemNavi is an open remote-job-market index that aggregates publicly accessible remote job listings from seven major remote job boards and ATS platforms – *Jobicy, Remote OK, We Work Remotely, Remotive, Greenhouse, Lever, and Hacker News Who's Hiring* – supplemented by specialised boards and over sixty direct employer ATS career pages on Greenhouse, Ashby, and Lever. Every listing is scored on the Real Remote Score (RRS), a public 100-point five-pillar transparency rubric (Compensation 30; Location 25; Source 20; Role Clarity 15; Freshness 10). Hybrid roles additionally carry a parallel Hybrid Transparency Score (HTS).

This document is v1 of the RemNavi methodology. It describes the source inventory, ingestion cadence, deduplication rules, salary data treatment, the RRS and HTS scoring rubrics, the scope of the index, the commercial model and editorial firewall, known limitations and biases, and the open-data licence and reproducibility conditions. The methodology is designed to allow third-party researchers, journalists, and data scientists to reproduce, audit, and cite RemNavi's measurements of the remote job market – in particular in connection with the EU Pay Transparency Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/970).

Keywords: remote work; job market analytics; salary transparency; EU Pay Transparency Directive; data aggregation; transparency rubric; open data; CC BY 4.0; web data; labour-market measurement.

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1. Introduction

RemNavi is a remote job aggregator. It collects job listings from publicly accessible sources, normalises the fields, scores each listing on a public transparency rubric, and presents the result under a single searchable interface. RemNavi does not host listings, does not receive applications, and does not act as a recruitment intermediary; every listing links directly to the employer's own application page.

This document establishes v1 of the methodology. It is intended as a citable reference for researchers, journalists, regulators, and data scientists using RemNavi data or analyses. The live, continuously-updated version of the methodology is published at <https://remnavi.com/methodology/>. The full Real Remote Score rubric, including per-pillar scoring rules, is published at <https://remnavi.com/real-remote-score-methodology/>. Subsequent revisions of this methodology will be deposited as new versions of the present Zenodo record.

2. Data sources

All listings come from publicly accessible job boards and ATS-hosted career pages. RemNavi does not scrape behind a login, does not bypass robots directives, and does not access non-public data. Every listing links directly to the source so that applications happen at the employer.

2.1 Seven major source platforms

The canonical inventory of sources used in RemNavi v1 consists of seven platforms:

- **Jobicy** – curated remote board with structured salary disclosure.
- **Remote OK** – high-volume remote board with structured salary fields.
- **We Work Remotely** – long-running remote board with eleven category feeds.
- **Remoteive** – remote-first board with strong SaaS employer coverage.
- **Greenhouse** – direct employer ATS; integrated with 30+ remote-hiring company career pages (including Stripe, Cloudflare, Anthropic, Okta, HubSpot, and Duolingo).
- **Lever** – direct employer ATS; integrated with three remote-hiring company career pages.
- **Hacker News Who's Hiring** – monthly community thread parsed for structured fields.

2.2 Specialised and complementary sources

In addition to the seven major platforms, the corpus draws from the following specialised sources to extend category coverage:

- **Himalayas** – remote-only board with salary and company-culture data.
- **Working Nomads** – curated remote board, tech and digital roles.

- Arbeitnow – European remote and tech job board with a public API.
- 4 Day Week – remote roles at companies with a 4-day or flexible work week.
- Crypto Jobs List – niche board for web3 and blockchain roles.
- Golang Projects – Go-specific job board.
- Python.org Jobs – official Python community board.
- VueJobs – Vue.js-specific board.
- Ashby – direct employer ATS; integrated with 25+ remote-hiring company career pages (including Retool, Perplexity, Cursor, Supabase, and Vanta).

2.3 Source inventory and traceability

Counted by distinct upstream feed, the corpus draws from approximately 70 active sources as of 2026-05-15 and grows as new ATS company integrations are added. Every listing in the live dataset carries a source-attribution field that records the upstream feed it was retrieved from; this field is preserved in the public CSV and JSON exports so that downstream researchers can subset by source.

2.4 Source inclusion criteria

New sources are evaluated on three criteria before inclusion: (a) coverage breadth – does the source materially expand the set of remote roles captured?; (b) salary-field discipline – does the source publish structured numeric salary data?; (c) content quality – does the source filter for legitimate listings rather than mass-aggregating unverified postings? Sources that meet these criteria are added to the polling schedule and become visible in the corpus on the next ingestion cycle.

3. Ingestion cadence

All sources are polled every six hours via a scheduled cron job. Each source is fetched in sequence within a single run – board APIs (Jobicy, Remote OK, Remotive, Himalayas, and others), RSS feeds, Greenhouse / Ashby / Lever career pages, and the monthly Hacker News Who's Hiring thread. A full cycle typically completes in under sixty seconds.

A listing is removed from RemNavi when its source no longer returns it in the latest poll. Because RemNavi prunes per-source on each successful fetch, a job that closes on the employer's side is removed from the index within six hours.

4. Deduplication

RemNavi deduplicates on URL. Each unique application URL is stored exactly once, regardless of how many upstream feeds link to it. If the same URL appears across multiple sources – for example, a Greenhouse posting that is also syndicated to Remotive – it is stored

once. The second fetch backfills any missing fields (salary, description) without creating a duplicate record.

Jobs that exist at both an ATS source and an aggregator board under different URLs (a pattern common with Jobicy, Remotive, and Working Nomads) appear as separate records. In practice this affects a minority of listings. Title-plus-company hash deduplication is planned for a subsequent methodology version and will prefer the direct ATS link where both exist.

5. Salary data

5.1 Inclusion rules

The Remote Salary Index surfaces only listings with transparent, structured compensation. RemNavi does not fabricate ranges, infer them from proxies, or interpolate between employers. A listing enters the Salary Index only if the source provides a numeric range or a single numeric figure. Free-text salary language ("competitive", "market rate", "DOE") is excluded.

5.2 Currency normalisation

Every salary range is converted to US dollars per year using a daily FX rate. Cost-of-living adjustment is not applied at this layer; it is handled separately in the Salary Calculator tool. The FX conversion preserves the original currency and original numeric values in the underlying record so that downstream researchers can re-run their own normalisations.

5.3 Aggregation rules

RemNavi reports median and range per role group and per seniority band. Groups with fewer than five listings in the current window are suppressed to avoid statistical noise. The published snapshot is rebuilt at every release and exposes the row-level underlying data under CC BY 4.0 at <https://remnavi.com/tools/salary-index/>.

6. The Real Remote Score (RRS)

Every listing in the RemNavi corpus is scored on the Real Remote Score, a public 100-point rubric that measures how genuinely remote a job listing is. The score is computed deterministically from the listing's structured metadata and the source feed. The score is computed identically for every listing regardless of any commercial relationship with the employer.

6.1 Pillar weights

The RRS aggregates five weighted pillars:

- **Compensation transparency** – 30 points. Numeric salary range, single figure, or structured equity disclosure.

- **Location openness** – 25 points. Geographic scope of eligibility (global, regional, country, sub-country).
- **Source credibility** – 20 points. Direct ATS career page > curated board > aggregator board > parsed thread.
- **Role clarity** – 15 points. Seniority specificity, stack/tooling disclosure, employment type.
- **Listing freshness** – 10 points. Days since posted, with diminishing credit beyond thirty days.

6.2 Computation and versioning

Per-pillar scoring rules, edge cases, and the current rubric version are published in full at <https://remnavi.com/real-remote-score-methodology/>. The rubric is versioned: each change to weights or per-pillar rules is published with an effective date, and historical scoring is preserved on listings in the underlying dataset. This allows time-series analyses across rubric versions.

7. The Hybrid Transparency Score (HTS)

RemNavi additionally scores hybrid listings – roles that are not fully remote but allow some remote work – on a parallel rubric, the Hybrid Transparency Score. The HTS measures how clearly the listing discloses in-office days, schedule pattern, office location, and relocation policy. The HTS is reported separately from the RRS so that the two questions – "is this actually remote?" and "if hybrid, has the employer disclosed enough?" – are never conflated. The full HTS rubric is published alongside the RRS rubric on the live methodology pages.

8. Scope and boundaries

Explicit statements of what RemNavi is not are more useful to researchers than hedge-everything disclaimers.

- RemNavi is not a job board. It does not host job postings, does not receive applications, and does not store applicant data. Every listing links to the employer's own application page.
- RemNavi offers featured placement for eligible public listings – the role must be fully remote, link to the employer's own application URL, and otherwise meet the standard inclusion criteria. Featured slots buy visibility, not inclusion: payment cannot place an ineligible role on the site, and every featured unit is clearly labelled. Payment does not affect the Real Remote Score, salary data, or rankings outside the labelled featured slot.
- RemNavi is not a recruiting agency. It does not hold candidate profiles, does not submit applications, and does not broker between candidates and employers.

- Salary figures published by RemNavi are not a compensation benchmark. They are a live snapshot of what employers openly advertise – useful as a negotiation anchor or a measurement of disclosure, not as an authoritative industry rate.
- The Real Remote Score is a public scoring rubric, not an endorsement. Employers cannot pay to influence their score, and the score is computed from the same signals whether or not a role is featured.

9. Commercial model and editorial firewall

RemNavi earns revenue from clearly-labelled Featured Listings, sponsorships, and affiliate relationships with Employer-of-Record providers, payroll platforms, and job-aggregator partners.

The editorial firewall is absolute and covers every revenue line. No form of revenue – Featured Listings, affiliate, or sponsorship – affects RRS or HTS scores, leaderboard position, ranked editorial views, or which companies are included in coverage. A company can be a paying advertiser or an affiliate partner and still appear anywhere in RemNavi’s rankings, including at the bottom. That outcome is the firewall working as intended.

Where a company named in a ranked editorial piece – a Market Index issue, a leaderboard, an award – also holds an affiliate relationship with RemNavi, that relationship is disclosed within that piece.

10. Limitations and known biases

10.1 Salary-disclosure sample bias

The Salary Index sample is biased toward employers who publish salary bands. In practice this means US-headquartered SaaS employers, European remote-first companies, and European employers subject to the 2026 EU Pay Transparency Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/970) are overrepresented. US states with pay-transparency laws (California, Colorado, New York, Washington) are correspondingly overrepresented in the underlying data. Medians published from this sample should be interpreted as lower-bound signals of openly-advertised compensation, not as universal industry figures.

10.2 Duplicate-source records

A minority of listings appear as separate records when the same role is posted to both an ATS source and an aggregator board under different URLs. Title-plus-company hash deduplication is planned for a subsequent methodology version to consolidate these and prefer the direct ATS link.

10.3 Cost-of-living adjustment

The Salary Index does not apply cost-of-living adjustment. This is intentional at the index layer: the published figures describe what employers advertise, not what those figures buy in different markets. The separate Salary Calculator tool handles cost-of-living comparisons for downstream user-facing analysis.

10.4 Non-EU and non-US corpus coverage

RemNavi's source platforms are predominantly Anglophone and US/EU-centred. Remote-job listings outside this orbit – for example LATAM- or APAC-specific local boards – are underrepresented in v1. Subsequent methodology versions will broaden the source list as suitable feeds are identified and meet the inclusion criteria.

11. Data availability and reproducibility

The structured data underlying RemNavi is published continuously and made openly available at the following endpoints:

- **Remote Salary Index (CSV + JSON):** <https://remnavi.com/tools/salary-index/>
- **Market Index (source, role, skill, company, geography, seniority cuts):** <https://remnavi.com/market-index/>
- **Trends API (historical time series):** <https://remnavi.com/trends/>

All endpoints carry the source-attribution field and the per-listing RRS, enabling third parties to reproduce RemNavi's aggregate statistics from the row-level data. Endpoints are versioned and stable; breaking changes will be announced on the methodology page with a deprecation window.

12. Licence and attribution

The structured data underlying the Remote Salary Index and the broader Market Index is published under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). Commercial reuse is permitted under the same terms.

Suggested attribution: "**RemNavi – <https://remnavi.com>**", and, for academic or journalistic citation of the methodology itself, the citation block on the title page of this document.

Individual job listings remain the intellectual property of the source employer and posting platform. RemNavi's aggregation of publicly accessible listings operates consistently with EU database and information-society directives applicable to lawful aggregators of public data. RemNavi does not store full job descriptions – only the metadata required for discovery and the canonical link back to the source. Employers who would like a specific listing removed or a source excluded should write to hello@remnavi.com; requests are actioned within 48 hours.

13. References

- [1] European Parliament & Council of the European Union (2023). *Directive (EU) 2023/970 on strengthening the application of the principle of equal pay for equal work or work of equal value between men and women through pay transparency and enforcement mechanisms (the EU Pay Transparency Directive)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/970>
- [2] Creative Commons. *Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) deed and legal code*. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- [3] RemNavi (live). *RemNavi Methodology – live, continuously updated reference page*. <https://remnavi.com/methodology/>
- [4] RemNavi (live). *Real Remote Score Methodology – five-pillar transparency rubric (live reference)*. <https://remnavi.com/real-remote-score-methodology/>
- [5] RemNavi (live). *Remote Salary Index (CSV + JSON), licensed under CC BY 4.0*. <https://remnavi.com/tools/salary-index/>
- [6] RemNavi (live). *Market Index – multi-dimensional cuts (source, role, skill, company, geography, seniority)*. <https://remnavi.com/market-index/>

14. Version history

v1.0 – 2026-05-15. Initial Zenodo deposit. Establishes the v1 baseline methodology for source aggregation, ingestion cadence, deduplication, salary data treatment, the Real Remote Score and Hybrid Transparency Score rubrics, the commercial model and editorial firewall, and the CC BY 4.0 data licence. Approximately 8,750 live listings at deposit, drawn from seven major source platforms supplemented by specialised boards and 60+ direct ATS career pages.

Subsequent methodological revisions will be deposited as new versions of this Zenodo record. Each revision will preserve the prior version, document changes in this section, and update the suggested-citation block on the title page accordingly.

Contact

Press and citation enquiries: **press@remnavi.com**

Corrections and source/listing removal requests: **hello@remnavi.com**

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The live, dated version of the RemNavi methodology is always available at <https://remnavi.com/methodology/>.